

The Tales of Series: Capturing the Players' Hearts (Part II)

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Continuing from the first part of this article, which was divided into two sections to avoid an excessively long single piece, as has been done on previous occasions, we proceed with the history of the Tales of franchise, from the era of PlayStation 2, GameCube, and Xbox to the present day. The Tales of series includes a number of titles comparable to other franchises such as Dragon Quest, and we did not want to overlook the mainline games, as would have occurred in a single article.

The Tales of Saga in the Sixth Generation of Consoles

The next instalment in the Tales of series, the fourth, *Tales of Destiny 2*, was released in 2002, beginning its development shortly after *Tales of Eternia* was published. It was released internationally, and in 2007 a portable version for Sony's PlayStation Portable was made available —however, this version was only published in Japan and South Korea. It was the last game developed by Wolf Team before becoming Namco Tales Studio. *Tales of Destiny 2* featured the Characteristic Genre “Liberating Fate RPG”.

It is the first Tales game to break with the tradition of telling a story unrelated to a previous title, as its very name indicates: it is a direct sequel to *Tales of Destiny*, narrating events that take place eighteen years after the conclusion of the first game on PlayStation.

The story follows the adventures of Kyle Dunamis, son of Stahn Aileron, protagonist of the original *Tales of Destiny*, and Rutee Katria. Kyle attempts to save Rutee's orphanage from bankruptcy —where he himself resides after losing his father Stahn— but he encounters Barbatos, a warrior responsible for Stahn's death.

Kyle sets out on an adventure with his best friend, Loni —whom he considers a brother, having grown up alongside him—, and they discover a Lens stone —the mysterious energy source from space introduced in the first game—. Moments later, Reala appears, claiming to be in search of a hero.

When Kyle is captured by the army seeking the lost Lens stones, he manages to escape with the help of a mysterious swordsman named Judas, and learns that the enigmatic Barbatos was responsible for killing his father’s team members as well as Stahn himself.

Kyle and his team must face numerous challenges, including the schemes of the mysterious Elrane, a religious leader who uses the power of the Lens stones to perform miracles. Later in the plot, Kyle and his companions travel to the future and discover that both Reala and Elrane are avatars of the goddess Fortuna. Elrane is revealed to be orchestrating Barbatos’s actions —he is a resurrected warrior from the Aeth’er Wars— and responsible for the resurrection of Judas, who is in fact Leon, Stahn’s comrade-in-arms who betrayed Stahn’s team. The entire scheme is Elrane’s plan to alter the course of history, and Kyle and his friends must fight to restore the natural flow of time —resulting in Judas’s disappearance and Stahn’s survival.

Motoi Sakuraba, the series’ regular composer, returned for this title alongside Shinji Tamura —also a frequent contributor to the Tales team—, and once again, Production I.G handled the animated sequences integrated into the game.

Concept art for *Tales of Destiny 2* by Mutsumi Inomata, with Kyle Dunamis on the left and Reala on the right

Following *Tales of Destiny 2*, the Tales of series returned to a Nintendo console with the notable release of *Tales of Symphonia* in 2003 for GameCube. Although it was also released on PlayStation 2, later versions became available on PlayStation 3 and PC. Its Characteristic Genre is “Resonating with you RPG”. A compilation called *Tales of Symphonia Chronicles* was later released for PlayStation 3, which included the original game and its sequel, *Tales of Symphonia: Dawn of the New World*. The game follows the adventures of Lloyd Irving, who accompanies his childhood friend Colette Brunel, a young woman chosen by destiny to save her world, Sylvarant, alongside another friend, Genis Sage. The three are also classmates. As the plot unfolds, the protagonists discover that, in continuing to fight to protect Sylvarant, they are inadvertently causing irreparable damage to Tethe’alla, a parallel world.

Kratos Aurion and Raine Sage —Genis’s sister— are Colette’s guardians, aiding her on the journey to remove the seal divided across five temples, which will allow the power of mana to save Sylvarant. Sheena Fujibayashi is another character the protagonists encounter, who reveals the harsh reality that while they remove the seals and restore Sylvarant, Tethe’alla will suffer the consequences. Lloyd and his friends resolve to discover how to save both worlds with the guidance of the angel Remiel, but he, along with Colette’s guardian Kratos, are revealed to be traitors, members of the organisation Cruxis serving the true villain of this game, Mithos Yggdrasil.

The heroes manage to restore both worlds by awakening the summoning spirits of each, which dissolve the mana bond, preventing Sylvarant from harming Tethe’alla. Later, after stabilising the Mana Seed, which had been affected by the actions of Lloyd and his group while weakening the seals, the team fights to unify the two worlds using the power of the Eternal Sword. Kratos chooses to assist Lloyd’s team after defecting from Mithos’s ranks.

Tales of Symphonia is one of the most popular games in the series. As previously mentioned, it has seen multiple versions and is accompanied by seven drama CDs, seven manga collections, and two novels based on it, as well as the aforementioned sequel for Nintendo Wii, *Tales of Symphonia: Dawn of the New World* (2008).

On the left, Lloyd, and on the right, Kratos. Image from the third OVA of the *Sekai Tōgō Hen* —‘The Reunified World’—, which forms part of *Tales of Symphonia: The Animation*, the animated adaptation of *Tales of Symphonia*. This final part of the series was released in 2012.

Tales of Rebirth was the next title in the series, although misfortune meant that it was never released outside Japan, and to date, this game has not been officially available in any language other than Japanese. It was released in 2004 for PlayStation 2 and received a re-release for PlayStation Portable in 2008. Its Characteristic Genre is “Where You Will Be Reborn RPG”.

The game represents a return to the traditional 2D aesthetic, combining pre-rendered elements with sprites and three-dimensional models, always keeping in mind an anime-inspired style reminiscent of classic JRPGs from the 1980s and 1990s. Rather than offering an open world to explore freely as in other entries in the franchise, players select locations to visit via a map.

In the world of *Tales of Rebirth*, two species coexist —humans, or Huma, and beastmen, or Gajuma—, more or less peacefully. In this game, the power of magic is called “Force” —a clear homage to *Star Wars*. In the past, both species joined forces to create the kingdom of Calegia. When the Gajuma king dies mysteriously at the age of sixty, a new era of chaos begins. The protagonist, Veigue Lungberg, lives in a northern village constantly battered by cold.

Suddenly, the Huma become capable of using the Force, something that until then had only been wielded by the Gajuma. Veigue embarks on a quest for answers alongside his childhood friend Claire Bennett, who becomes a victim of this terrible power and is imprisoned in a block of ice. Geyorkias, the leader of the Sacred Beasts, had previously feared the humans’ power to awaken Yuris, an entity of immense strength, and waged war against them, ultimately capturing and sealing Yuris. During the events of the game, Geyorkias awakens and is defeated by the protagonists, but the racial tensions that arise as Yuris’s intentions are revealed threaten the fragile peace between beastmen and humans.

Following a series of events, the protagonists set out to revive the Sacred Beasts in order to end the conflicts and neutralise the threat posed by Yuris.

Screenshot of Tales of Rebirth

The next instalment in the Tales of series was *Tales of Legendia*, whose Characteristic Genre is “RPG Where Bonds Spin Legends”. It was released in 2005 in Japan and in 2006 in the United States, and once again featured three-dimensional models rather than sprites. The game was not developed solely by members of Namco Tales Studio; it also included staff who had worked on Namco’s Soul Calibur and Tekken series.

The protagonist of this game is Senel Coolidge, a young man who must embark on a quest to rescue his “adoptive sister,” Shirley Fennes, who has been kidnapped by a group that believes her to be the saviour of the Ferine race, a “Merine.” This game presents a world submerged in water, where much of the action takes place aboard a ship that is itself a relic from a bygone age. The population is divided between the Orerines —people living on land, or rather atop the remnants of past civilizations, such as the aforementioned ship— and the Ferines, who can breathe underwater and thus live beneath the surface.

Both races live under constant tension, and to complicate matters further, there is a third group, the “Eren,” individuals capable of using various supernatural powers such as magic, as well as enhanced physical abilities for hand-to-hand combat or weapon attacks. Moses, initially responsible for kidnapping Shirley, ultimately decides to make amends and joins Senel’s group.

The protagonists discover that the ship on which they lived, called *Legacy*, is actually a vessel populated by settlers from another planet, and that the Ferines arrived 4,000 years ago to wage war on the Orerines. However, the plot twists when the characters realise that it was, in fact, the Orerines who came from another planet. After defeating Maurits Welnes, one of the Ferine leaders, Senel’s group convinces him to change his mindset and help broker peace between the Ferines and Orerines, preventing the impending catastrophe caused by the creature Nerifes, which had attempted to possess Shirley and had then taken control of Maurits.

Combat screen from *Tales of Legendia*. As can be seen, it retains the series’ style with side-view battles, regardless of whether the elements displayed are in 3D.

Tales of the Abyss followed *Legendia*, with its Characteristic Genre being “Discovering the Meaning of Life RPG”. It was first released for PlayStation 2 in 2005, and later re-released for Nintendo 3DS in 2011. It was the eighth main title in the series, and coincided with the tenth anniversary of the birth of the Tales of franchise.

The story of *Tales of the Abyss* takes place on the planet Auldrant, which is said to be composed entirely of particles called “fonons”. Of these, only six were previously known. Luke von Fabre, a descendant of the Fabre house, suddenly finds himself caught up in a plot centred on the discovery of a seventh fonon, related to sound, which allows those who understand its secrets to gain knowledge of the future.

Luke suffers from amnesia and is unable even to leave his home, as he is being trained to inherit the leadership of the von Fabre household. Suddenly, his mentor, Van Grants, is attacked by a mysterious fonist—an expert in the study of fonons— named Tear Grants. Tear and Luke are swept away from the mansion, and Tear reveals to Luke that he too has the potential to become a fonist of the seventh fonon.

Initially, Luke regards Tear as an enemy, but they decide to set aside their differences and work together to uncover the truth about what is happening between them. This is once again the classic RPG (and anime) twist, in which characters begin as adversaries, gradually become allies, and vice versa, creating tension that compels the player to continue discovering the story. Van Grants, Luke’s mentor, is eventually revealed to be the main antagonist of the game.

Later in the story, Luke learns that Tear actually comes from a continent called Qliphoth, located beneath the surface of their world, which is now entirely engulfed by the miasma. Luke’s journey ultimately reveals that he himself is a replica of the God-General Asch, and that Van’s plan involves creating a replica of the world; for this plan to succeed, the original must be destroyed. Luke ultimately sacrifices himself alongside Asch to save his world, and both appear as a single being in the game’s epilogue.

Tear Grants and Luke von Fabre in a scene from the 2008 *Tales of the Abyss* anime, produced by the studio Sunrise

The Seventh Generation of Consoles: The Tales of Series Established in the International Market

The first title released in the next generation of video game consoles was a portable Tales of entry belonging to the main series, *Tales of Innocence*. It was developed by Alfa System —rather than Namco Tales Studio—.

It was released on Nintendo DS in 2007, and its Characteristic Genre is “Connecting Thoughts RPG”. Despite the title of this section, this Tales game was not released outside Japan, and the poor sales of the PlayStation Vita in the West —according to the game’s production team— also prevented its updated version, *Innocence R* (2012), from being released internationally —although later titles did reach Western markets without this justification being cited—.

In this title, the game world is divided into two realms: Devaloka —the divine realm— and Naraka —the human world, located below—. Two regions of Devaloka, Sensus and Ratio, went to war due to the ambition of certain leaders to unify both worlds in order to harvest human souls —necessary for the survival of Devaloka’s inhabitants—. Asura was the general behind this plan of unification, and the protagonist of this title, Ruca Milda, is his reincarnation. Western audiences had to wait until 2008 to receive a new entry in the Tales of series: *Tales of Vesperia*, whose Characteristic Genre is “Enforcing One’s Justice RPG”.

The events of *Vesperia* take place on the planet Terca Lumireis. Its inhabitants rely on a technology known as “blastia”, originating from an ancient civilisation, which possesses a wide range of abilities and functions, serving both as a source of energy and as a means of creating protective barriers. The Krytians are responsible for developing this power through the use of “aer”, a substance that can be lethal to humans. Yuri Lowell is the protagonist of the story and, as is often the case throughout the series, he finds himself imprisoned after attempting to uncover the thief of a blastia core, the loss of which causes flooding among the poorer districts of Zaphias. His journey leads him to save the world alongside a group of companions, including his dog Repede and Estellise Sidos Heurassein, as they attempt to harness blastia technology to restore balance to the world.

Image from *Tales of Vesperia: Definitive Edition* (2019), released for Nintendo Switch, PlayStation 4, Xbox One, and PC

Tales of Hearts and its subsequent remake, *Tales of Hearts R*, constituted the next official entry in the series. It was originally released for the Nintendo DS, while its remake became part of the PlayStation Vita catalogue in 2013. This version was released in Western markets and featured improved graphics, as well as the possibility of having three characters controlled by artificial intelligence instead of two, as in the original DS version.

On the Nintendo DS, two versions of the game existed: one that offered animated sequences for key story moments in the form of CGI cinematics —computer-generated imagery—, and another that presented these scenes through traditional animation produced by the Production I.G team. Its Characteristic Genre is “A Meeting Between Hearts RPG”, and “A New Meeting Between Hearts RPG” in the remake version. It was also released on iOS.

The game introduced a new combat mechanic, whereby different button combinations triggered a variety of attacks and combos. The story follows the young Kor Meteor, who soon encounters Kohaku and her protective brother Hisui Hearts, as they search for a “Soma” —the name given to the power used by characters in this game— for Kohaku. Other characters join them, such as the honourable Chalcedony, the war machine Kunzite, and the “elder” Gall Gruner —the latter only in *Tales of Hearts R*.

The Soma plays a vital role in the game, and weapons can even be customised using different materials to increase statistics or unlock new abilities, such as evasive manoeuvres and dodging skills.

Tales of Graces was the next entry, being the twelfth main title and the tenth developed by the team formed by Namco Tales Studio —formerly Wolf Team—. Its Characteristic Genre is “Discovering the Strength to Protect RPG”. It was first released on the Nintendo Wii in 2009 and later on the PlayStation 3 in 2010.

In this game, players are transported to the world of Ephinea, whose inhabitants depend entirely on the power of monuments known as “Valkines Cryas”, which grant them “Eleth”, a substance upon which life on the planet depends. There are three types of Valkines Cryas, and they become central to a plot involving the protagonist, Asbel Lhant, and his companions, encompassing conspiracies, betrayals, and constant warfare.

The plot becomes significantly more complex in the PlayStation 3 version, which also adds an additional story set six months after the end of the original game —hence the title *Tales of Graces f*, where the “f” stands for “future”—.

Only one year after the PlayStation 3 version of *Tales of Graces*, Namco released *Tales of Xillia*, whose Characteristic Genre is “RPG of Unwavering Convictions”. It was released outside Japan two years later, in 2013, much to the delight of fans of the series.

It received a sequel, *Tales of Xillia 2* —once again breaking with the more or less established tradition of not continuing the story of a main entry— in 2012. For both *Xillia* and its sequel, the animated sequences were produced by the studio Ufotable. Both games share the same universe, with *Xillia 2* taking place one year after the end of the first instalment.

Xillia was the last game in the franchise developed by the iconic Namco Tales Studio, with subsequent entries being produced by Bandai Namco Studios in collaboration with other development teams.

It was also pioneering in allowing players to choose between two main playable protagonists, Jude Mathis and Milla Maxwell, thus altering the course of the story depending on the player's decisions. The Characteristic Genre of the sequel is “Choices that Spin the Future RPG”.

The Tales of Series Today

The first instalment to appear on the following generation of consoles was *Tales of Zestiria* (2015), released for both PlayStation 3 and PlayStation 4. Interestingly, it also has a version for the Steam platform (PC), although this version was not released in Japan.

Fujishima and Inomata once again collaborated on the character design —throughout the history of the Tales of series, they have alternated or worked together—, joined in this title by Daigo Okumura and Minoru Iwamoto. Once again, Motoi Sakuraba served as the main composer, working alongside Gō Shiina.

The narrative of this instalment shows a clear homage to the Warhammer 40,000 series by Games Workshop, in which the emotions of sentient races give rise to dark powers. However, rather than belonging to another dimension, in *Zestiria* this takes the form of “malevolence”, a substance that transforms everything it touches into monsters known as “hellions”, which constitute the primary threat faced by the protagonists, Sorey and Mikleo, throughout their journey. Unlike previous titles, battles do not occur after a loading screen or a change of environment, but instead take place seamlessly within the same area being explored. Its Characteristic Genre is “Passion that Illuminates the World RPG”.

Sorey —left— and Mikleo —centre—, facing Alisha Diphda —right, seen from behind—. Screenshot from an in-engine animated sequence from *Tales of Zestiria*.

The next main instalment in the series was a prequel titled *Tales of Berseria*, released in 2016 for PlayStation 3 —exclusively in Japan—, and for PlayStation 4 and PC in 2016 —Japan— and 2017 —rest of the world—. Its Characteristic Genre was “RPG of Discovering Your Own Reasons to Live”.

Berseria introduced further changes to the combat system, which now allows players to move characters freely across the battlefield and rotate the camera at will, as in other role-playing games. The “Soul Gauge” prevents the game from becoming a mere button-mashing experience, as it forces players to maintain a rhythm when attacking opponents; if attacks are executed with the gauge depleted, they become easily avoidable. Additionally, enemies can steal part of this gauge and use it to their advantage.

When the gauge is full, players can perform transformations or special attacks depending on the character and the artes they possess. *Berseria* even allows for local cooperative play during battles.

The game world is known as “Desolation”, and the events take place specifically in the Holy Midgand Empire, within the same universe as *Tales of Zestiria*, but many years earlier, in a distant past. The protagonist, Velvet Crowe, a determined and highly powerful young woman skilled both in weaponry and demonic artes, joins forces with Laphicet Crowe, her younger brother. Together, they fight to rid their world of malevolence —which Velvet is able to absorb at will through her demonic arm—, a concept that also played a major role in *Zestiria*, set in the future.

Other titles within the franchise that do not belong to the main series include games such as *Tales of Eternia Online* —active from 2006 to 2007—, as well as numerous spin-offs for mobile devices, such as *Tales of Tactics* —based on SRPGs like the Fire Emblem series by Intelligent Systems or the Ogre series by Atlus—. Several entries, including *Tales of Destiny*, *Tales of Graces*, and *Tales of Xillia*, are still awaiting anime adaptations —while *Berseria* and *Zestiria* were adapted through the anime *Tales of Zestiria the X*, released in 2017, which does not strictly follow the events of either game—.

While many franchises lose their identity by introducing excessive changes, or conversely stagnate by failing to evolve, this has not been the case with the *Tales of* series, despite its more than 30-year trajectory. That said, it is also true that the narratives of its various instalments tend to rely on recurring clichés —most of them drawn from anime and manga, and likely included deliberately—.

Among the features that have unified the main *Tales of* series are the Linear Motion Battle System, in which players can move from left to right within the battle field —although in some instalments both character movement and camera control are more flexible—, as well as the inclusion of optional side interactions known as “skits”, which enrich character relationships. Another recurring element throughout the series —and one of the reasons why a detailed analysis of each individual plot has not been undertaken— is the coexistence of different sentient races within each world, and how the irresponsible use of their powers can lead to catastrophe, prompting the protagonists to restore balance and peace among the various species and peoples of their respective universes.

A significant portion of the original development team behind the first *Tales of — Phantasia—*, including Yoshiharu Gotanda, left Wolf Team due to contractual issues and went on to work on franchises such as *Star Ocean*, while the remaining members stayed within the renamed Namco Tales Studio to continue developing future instalments. Namco eventually integrated both the original staff and the studio into Bandai Namco Studios.

Velvet Crowe, rendered using the game engine of *Tales of Berseria*.

After a period of technological and structural transition within the company, the saga took a significant qualitative leap with *Tales of Arise*, released in 2021 for PlayStation 4, PlayStation 5, Xbox One, Xbox Series X|S, and PC. This title marked a major graphical modernization thanks to the use of Unreal Engine 4, offering a more realistic and cinematic visual finish than previous entries.

Its characteristic genre, “RPG of Rising,” embodies a narrative centred on colonial oppression between the worlds of Dahna and Rena. The story follows Alphen and Shionne, representatives of peoples who have been in conflict for centuries due to slavery and energy domination based on the extraction of “astral energy.” The work delves into themes such as structural inequality, the dehumanization of the enemy, and the construction of collective identities in the aftermath of trauma.

From a gameplay perspective, the combat system definitively abandons the classic linear movement to adopt a more open three-dimensional environment, while still retaining the essence of the Linear Motion Battle System through chained combos and cooperative “Boost Strikes.” *Arise* also marked a significant international commercial success, firmly consolidating the franchise in the global market.

In 2023, *Tales of Symphonia Remastered* was released for Nintendo Switch, PlayStation 4, and Xbox One. This re-release highlighted the enduring relevance of one of the most influential titles in the saga, though it also sparked debate among the community due to technical limitations inherited from previous versions.

The remaster underscores the symbolic weight of *Symphonia* within the franchise's history, serving as a bridge between the two-dimensional classicism and the subsequent three-dimensional consolidation. Its re-release reaffirms the importance of historical preservation of JRPGs within the contemporary ecosystem.

Following the recent policy of reviving the historical catalogue, *Tales of Graces f Remastered* was launched in 2025 for modern platforms. This title, remembered for one of the most technical and polished combat systems in the saga, refocused attention on the mechanical dimension of combat, in contrast with the greater narrative emphasis of *Arise*.

Its return allowed for a renewed appreciation of the “Style Shift Linear Motion Battle System,” one of the franchise's most strategic systems, characterized by the management of “Chain Capacity” and alternating combat styles.

As of 2026, the Tales of saga is in a stage of international consolidation and heritage review. No new numbered entry after *Arise* has been officially announced, although Bandai Namco has maintained interest through remasters, commemorative events, and additional content—such as the *Beyond the Dawn* expansion for *Tales of Arise* in 2023.

From a historical perspective, it can be stated that the franchise has entered a phase of industrial maturity. While the early decades were marked by technical experimentation and the consolidation of its aesthetic identity, the post-2020 period shows a clear intent to balance technological modernization with respect for gameplay tradition.

The saga continues to revolve around recognizable thematic constants: the conflictive coexistence of races or peoples, the irresponsible use of energy sources, critique of hierarchical power structures, and personal redemption through emotional bonds—elements that have made it one of the most coherent franchises that has not lost its identity within contemporary JRPGs.

Sources

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